

Interim report on coupled model developments

C3S2_370_MF – Operational production of seasonal forecasts

Issued by: Météo-France / Jean-François Guérémy

Date: 03/05/2023

Ref:

C3S2_D370.3.1.1_202304_Interim_Report_coupled_model_developments_v1

Official reference number service contract: 2021/C3S2_370_MF/SC1

Contributors

METEO-FRANCE

Jean-François Guérémy

Constantin Ardilouze

Lauriane Batté

Jonathan Beuvier

Laurent Dorel

Damien Specq

Fousiya Thottuvilampil Shahul Hameed

Table of contents

1. Executive summary	p. 5
2. Introduction	p. 5
3. Atmospheric component	p. 6
4. Oceanic component	p. 13
5. Continental surface component	p. 15
6. Initial conditions, ensemble size and generation	p. 16
7. Conclusions	p. 18

1. Executive summary

This deliverable provides an update on the current coupled model developments implemented and tested for possible inclusion in the next generation of the Météo-France seasonal prediction system. This work builds on developments on the different components of the CNRM-CM coupled climate model, and on specific integration and testing performed as part of task 3.1 of the present C3S2-370-MF contract.

The main scope of the document is to provide an update on the development of candidate versions for the different components of the climate system (atmosphere, ocean, sea ice and land surface), alongside an assessment – where relevant – of the current impact these candidate versions could have on seasonal forecast quality.

This interim report also includes considerations related to task 3.2 on initial conditions and ensemble generation.

2. Introduction

The current Météo-France seasonal forecasting system (System 8, Météo-France, 2021) operated for the C3S2_370_MF contract is based on the CNRM-CM coupled climate model (version 6, Voltaire et al, 2019). In CNRM-CM, the atmosphere is simulated by the ARPEGE-Climat model (version 6). ARPEGE-Climat is coupled to the ocean model NEMO (version 3.6), while sea ice is represented by the GELATO model (version 6) embedded in NEMO. Finally, the coupled climate model also includes a representation of the land surface by the ISBA model combined with the CTRIP river routing component. In order to make seasonal forecasts from CNRM-CM, realistic initial conditions at a given date are provided by a coupled run where the CNRM-CM atmosphere and ocean are continuously nudged towards reanalysis or analysis data. Ensembles are generated through perturbations of the atmosphere dynamics using the stochastic dynamics approach described in Batté and Déqué (2016).

Since the release of System 8, research in the CNRM climate group and beyond has been carried out to improve the physical representation of the components in the climate model, while there is also ongoing work regarding the initialization strategy for the various model components. Our proposal in Task 3.1 is to integrate these new developments in a seasonal forecasting setup and compare the quality of the forecasts to those of the current operational System 8. The aim is to provide scientific input for the definition of an improved version of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting system (System 9), to be released in the second half of 2024.

This interim deliverable gives an overview of several developments around the CNRM-CM coupled model used for the production of Météo-France seasonal forecasts that have been carried out so far. Some of these developments are related to the components of the model itself, while others deal with its implementation in a seasonal forecasting context (initialization and ensemble generation). Section 3 is devoted to the atmospheric component, Section 4 to the oceanic

component, and Section 5 to the continental surface component. Several recommendations concerning the implementation of CNRM-CM for seasonal forecasts are presented in Section 6.

3. Atmospheric component

3.1. New formulation of atmospheric physics

Several changes in the physical parameterizations have been developed in ARPEGE-Climat since the release of System 8. As a result, there are currently two new physics schemes available, that are prospective candidates for the parameterizations in the atmosphere component of the upcoming Météo-France System 9 (S9). These two schemes share a common difference with System 8 in including the ecRad radiative scheme (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016), while they differ in the parameterization of convection.

The first set of parameterizations is an evolution of the physics scheme used in the CMIP6 version of the CNRM coupled model and in System 8 (see Météo-France 2021 for more details). This evolution developed by J.-F. Guérémy includes the PCMT convection scheme which computes deep and shallow convection (Guérémy 2011 and Piriou 2007). The main modifications to the current System 8 version relate to the turbulence scheme. The mixing length near the surface is reduced and heating due to TKE dissipation is activated, which leads to a less intense hydrological cycle and reduces surface evaporation by -2.5 Wm^{-2} in surface. This first set of atmospheric physics will be referred to as P6+ (enhancement of ARPEGE version 6 physics) in the following paragraphs.

A second set, referred to as P7 (candidate version for the future version 7 of ARPEGE-Climat) is developed by the Atmosphere component team of the Climate modelling group at CNRM, led by O. Geoffroy. It includes AROME shallow convection (Pergaud 2009) and IFS deep convection (Bechtold 2014) schemes.

Table 3.1.1 summarizes the main modifications in the atmospheric physics schemes to be compared: the currently operational System 8 physics and the new sets of parameterizations P6+ and P7.

Parameterization	System 8 (P6)	P6+	P7
Radiation	Longwave: Mlawer et al (1997) Shortwave: Morcrette (1990)	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016)	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016)
Deep convection	PCMT (Piriou et al 2007, Gueremy 2011)	PCMT (Piriou et al 2007, Gueremy 2011)	IFS deep convection (Bechtold et al, 2014)
Shallow convection	PCMT	PCMT	Pergaud et al (2009)
Turbulence	Cuxart et al (2000)	Cuxart et al (2000) with: - smaller mixing length close to surface - including heating due to TKE dissipation	Cuxart et al (2000)

Table 3.1.1. Summary of the main modifications in the atmosphere physics between Météo-France System 8 and the two candidate physics for System 9.

Twin re-forecast experiments (referred to as S9P6, S9P7) have been performed for the 4 main seasons (6 month range, 15 members) over 1993-2015 with each set of physics at their stage of development as of end of 2022. All re-forecasts started from the first of the month (in burst mode) with initial perturbations only. These re-forecasts have also been compared to the operational System 8 (S8).

In order to compare re-forecast experiments, we first computed SST (sea surface temperature) monthly time correlations averaged on the Nino3.4 box, over 1993-2015. Results are provided in Table 3.1.2., considering correlations averaged over the 4 start dates.

	S8	S9P6	S9P7
Months 2-4	0.906	0.926	0.924
Month 6	0.824	0.845	0.820

Table 3.1.2. Nino3.4 SST monthly time correlation averaged over the 4 start dates of 1993-2015. Reference: ERA5.

For months 2-4, this table shows that S9P6 and S9P7 correlations are equivalent, being significantly better than that of S8, at the significance level of 0.01 estimated by bootstrapping ensemble

members. At month 6, S9P6 correlation is significantly better than that of S8 and S9P7 which are both equivalent.

Secondly, we computed space correlations averaged over the 1993-2015 period for 3 selected variables Z500 (geopotential height at 500 hPa), PREC (precipitations) and ST (surface temperature) over 3 large domains NH (northern hemisphere 30°N-90°N), IT (inter-tropics 30°S-30°N) and SH (southern hemisphere 90°S-30°S). For each variable, the reference data for correlations is an ensemble of two difference datasets in order to take into account some uncertainty in the reference itself. For Z500 and ST, the two reanalysis ERA5 and JRA55 are considered, while PREC is verified against a combination of GPCP and MSWEP.

To compare the experiments, confidence intervals for correlation have been computed considering 80 random draws of 10 members out of the 15 available. The confidence interval is built using the median and the two extreme bounds at 2.5% of the Gaussian distribution that approximates those random draws. Given these confidence intervals, we define the following rules to achieve a quantitative comparison between two experiments:

- for IT domain, the 2 intervals must be disjoint for the correlations to be significantly different
- for extra-tropical domains, due to the smaller signal-to-noise ratio and to the small sample, the correlations are significantly different if the median of one experiment is outside (or on the bound of) the interval of the other experiment.

As an example, results for the spring season (MAM) are shown in Table 3.1.3.

	S9P6	S9P7
NH Z500	0.21 0.26 0.31	0.14 0.18 0.22
NH ST	0.35 0.37 0.39	0.33 0.35 0.38
IT PREC	0.42 0.43 0.43	0.45 0.46 0.47

Table 3.1.3. MAM space correlations with confidence intervals.

From results shown in Table 3.1.3, we conclude that for NH Z500, the median of S9P6 correlation (0.26) is larger than the upper bound of S9P7 (0.22); for NH ST, the lower bound of S9P6 correlation (0.35) is equal to the median of S9P7 (0.35); for IT PREC, the interval for S9P7 correlation results is higher than the interval of S9P6 results, both intervals being disjoint.

Table 3.1.4 summarizes these results in the first column and corresponding rows, alongside all the results for the four main seasons and different variables and regions of interest.

	MAM		JJA		SON		DJF	
	S9P7	S9P6	S9P7	S9P6	S9P7	S9P6	S9P7	S9P6
NH Z500								
NH PREC								
NH ST								
IT Z500								
IT PREC								
IT ST								
SH Z500								
SH PREC								
SH ST								

Table 3.1.4. Summary of comparisons between atmospheric physics sets, based on differences in spatial correlations over 1993-2015: green coloured cell indicates an improved score(see text).

To summarize, the correlation table shows that S9P7 is significantly better than S9P6 8 times, whereas S9P6 is significantly better than S9P7 9 times. Using the same approach as in Table 3.1.4, (not shown), it is also possible to compare the current operational System 8 with each new physics scheme. For instance, the comparison between S9P6 and System 8 across the 4 start dates shows that S9P6 is significantly better than S8 6 times, while S8 is better than S9P6 4 times.

Finally, taking all correlations into account (Table 3.1.2 and Table 3.1.4), it appears that both new physics scheme S9P6 and S9P7 exhibit similar performances, although slightly better for S9P6 overall. Moreover, it is clear that they both bring some improvement relative to the current System 8.

As an illustration, Figure 3.1.1 shows the grid point (on a 2.8° lon-lat grid) time correlation of PREC and Z500. As it was the case for the space correlations (see Table 3.1.4), one can see that S9P7 has the best correlations of IT PREC while S9P6 has the best correlations of NH Z500 and SH Z500 (regions circled in red in the figure).

Figure 3.1.1. SON time correlation; from top to bottom PREC and Z500, and from left to right S8, S9P6, S9P7.

3.2. Influence of interactive aerosols

Aerosols in System 8 are prescribed through a monthly climatology. This monthly climatology is generated by using the monthly means over 1995-2014 in a prior atmosphere-only historical run that incorporates an interactive aerosols module developed in ARPEGE-Climat (Michou et al, 2020). In this historical run, the wind is nudged towards reanalysis data (ERA-Interim) and the atmosphere is forced by sea surface temperature. The provided monthly climatology also has to be interpolated from the lower resolution of the historical run (TI127I91) to that of System 8 (TI359I137).

Instead of using such a climatology, a more realistic representation of aerosols in seasonal forecasts could be achieved by activating the interactive aerosols module directly in the forecast computation. A new set of re-forecasts including the interactive aerosols has been computed to assess the impact of such an increase in model complexity on forecast quality. Those re-forecasts are initialized from a prior coupled and nudged run at resolution TI359I137 similar to the System 8 initialization, except that interactive aerosols are also activated in this run to provide a consistent initialization of all components.

Twin re-forecast experiments have been performed over 1993-2015. These two experiments are referred to as S8b and S8ba, and are also compared to System 8. The relevant points for comparison between the three re-forecasts are indicated in Table 3.2.1 S8b is a control meant to mimic System 8 behaviour should the seasonal forecasting setup be the same as for the interactive aerosol test S8ba. Note that S8b and S8ba differ in two aspects: the physics scheme (operational physics P6 vs P6+ described in Section 3.1) and the interactive aerosols.

	S8	S8b	S8ba
Ensemble size	25	15	15
Available start dates	All 12 months	May, Nov.	Feb., May, Aug., Nov.
Initialization	Lagged initialization (see Météo-France, 2021)	Burst on 1 st of month	Burst on 1 st of month
Member generation	Stochastic dynamics (SD) Batté and Déqué (2016)	Stochastic dynamics (SD)	Stochastic dynamics (SD)
Physics scheme	P6	P6	P6+
Interactive aerosols	No	No	Yes

Table 3.2.1. Comparison between System 8 and the twin re-forecast experiments S8b and S8ba to study the impact of interactive aerosols.

The interactive aerosols module enables a better Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) long term evolution over the re-forecast period together with a better AOD year to year evolution. The Figure 3.2.1 shows the AOD for April in the climatology used in System 8 and for the years 1997 and 2012 in the S8ba re-forecast. The AOD increase over China clearly appears between 1997 and 2012.

Figure 3.2.1. AOD in April; from left to right Climatology, 1997 and 2012.

Moreover, in 2012 the AOD is particularly large over the north-east of India, which triggers a negative anomaly of the surface temperature in the observations, being better represented in S8ba compared to S8 (see Figure 3.2.2).

Figure 3.2.2. Surface Temperature (ST) anomaly in April 2012; from left to right Reanalyses (ERA5), S8 (NH ST ACC 0.59), S8ba (NH ST ACC 0.72).

In order to compare re-forecast experiments, we first computed SST monthly time correlations averaged on the Nino3.4 box, over 1993-2015. Results are provided in Table 3.2.2, considering correlations averaged over the available start dates (2 or 4).

	S8 (4sd)	S8ba (4sd)	S8 (2sd)	S8b (2sd)	S8ba (2sd)
Months 2-4	0.906	0.916	0.915	0.918	0.917
Month 6	0.824	0.827	0.836	0.834	0.842

Table 3.2.2. Nino3.4 SST monthly time correlation averaged over the 4 and 2 start dates of 1993-2015. Reference: ERA5.

For months 2-4, this table shows that S8ba correlation is significantly better than that of S8 over 4 start dates, at the significance level of 0.01 (estimated by bootstrapping ensemble members), while being equivalent for S8, S8b and S8ba over 2 start dates. At month 6, the correlations of each experiment are equivalent, either over 4 or 2 start dates.

Secondly, Table 3.2.3 presents the experiments S8b and S8ba classification according to spatial correlations over 1993-2015, as explained in section 3.1. Only S8b and S8ba are considered in the present Table 3.2.3, because these experiments have been performed in burst mode, while S8 used a lagged initialization.

	JJA		DJF	
	S8b	S8ba	S8b	S8ba
NH Z500				
NH PREC				
NH ST				
IT Z500				
IT PREC				

IT ST				
SH Z500				
SH PREC				
SH ST				

Table 3.2.3. Summary of comparisons between atmospheric physics sets, based on differences in spatial correlations over 1993-2015: green coloured cell indicates an improved score (see text).

To summarize, the correlation table shows that S8b is significantly better than S8ba 4 times. Considering 4 start dates, S8ba is better than S8 8 times, and S8 is better than S8ba 3 times. Taking Nino3.4 and hemispheric scores into account, it appears that S8ba performs slightly worse than S8b even if the interactive aerosols are providing some local (in space and time) skill. At the same time S8ba outperforms S8, the latter being handicapped by the lagged initialization (see section 6.4). Knowing that the interactive aerosol computational cost is of the order of +40%, an intermediate solution would be to consider moving averaged aerosol climatologies (computed from the prior nudged coupled run with interactive aerosols).

4. Oceanic component

4.1. Ocean and sea ice versions considered

Following the work done in the ocean component team from CNRM climate modelling group (retrieving and adapting NEMO codes to the Météo-France HPC environment), NEMOv4.2 including SI³ as new sea-ice model has been tested and compared to the version currently used in System 8, NEMOv3.6 with the sea-ice model Gelato. So far only forced simulations have been performed as a first stage before coupled simulations (NEMOv4.2 coupling being ongoing at the time of writing this report).

Figure 4.1.1 shows Arctic sea-ice thickness time evolution of forced simulations starting from analytical initial conditions. The orange curve corresponds to the forced run with NEMOv3.6-Gelato currently used for sea ice initialization in the operational System 8, provided by Mercator Ocean International. It uses ERA-Interim forcings and starts in 1992. The red curve corresponds to a similar forced run with the new model NEMOv4.2-SI³, using JRA55 forcings and starting in 1982 (first years not shown). Both runs are compared to PIOMAS as a reference. All forced simulations present a spin down, although that of SI³ is not visible since the simulation started in 1982. After spin down, SI³ reaches an equilibrium that is closer to PIOMAS than Gelato. Moreover, the annual cycle amplitude is too small with Gelato while being too large with SI³. According to experts at Mercator Ocean International (personal communication), some SI³ tuning (albedo notably, as done in Gelato) may correct part of this problem.

Figure 4.1.1. Arctic sea-ice thickness in PIOMAS reference dataset, NEMOv3.6-Gelato and NEMOv4.2-SI3 forced integrations.

Figure 4.1.2 compares Arctic sea-ice thickness time evolution of NEMOv3.6-Gelato forced simulation together with two coupled nudged simulations where NEMOv3.6-Gelato is coupled to ARPEGE-Climat. The simulation labelled EA7 is the one used for liquid ocean and atmosphere initialization of System 8, with the operational ARPEGE physics P6 and nudging of the atmosphere in temperature and wind. The nudged coupled simulation labelled EA10 differs from EA7 by using the new physics P6+ described in Section 3.1 and by including additional nudging in specific humidity.

In the nudged coupled integrations, the spin down is even more pronounced, providing too low values of sea-ice thickness during the warm season. The reader is reminded that this is why EA7 initial conditions for sea ice are not used in the operational System 8, but rather replaced by those of the NEMOv3.6-Gelato forced run. EA10 is better than EA7 on that respect, but still insufficient. It is therefore clear that a change in atmospheric physics will not solve this problem alone. However, considering the better results obtained with NEMOv4.2-SI³ compared to NEMOv3.6-Gelato in forced mode (see Figure 4.1.1), there is hope that the improvements will remain in coupled mode. Moreover, it is worth to note that the estimated computational cost in coupled mode with NEMO4.2-SI3 is of the order of -20% of that with NEMOv3.6-Gelato.

Figure 4.1.2. Arctic sea-ice thickness in PIOMAS, NEMOv3.6-Gelato forced (ERA1 forcings) and nudged coupled EA7 (with P6 physic) and EA10 (with P6+ physics).

In addition to the sea-ice thickness time series, Figure 4.1.3 presents the spatial pattern of this variable over the Arctic region for the month of September 1993 in PIOMAS, NEMOv3.6-Gelato and NEMOv4.2-SI³ forced simulations together with the nudged coupled simulation EA7. As expected from the two previous figures, all the simulated sea-ice is thinner than the reference. Nevertheless, as already discussed in the comments of Figure 4.1.1, albedo tuning in SI³ will increase sea-ice thickness during the warm season.

Figure 4.1.3. Sea-ice thickness over the north pole region for the month of September 1993 of PIOMAS, NEMOv3.6-Gelato and NEMOv4.2-SI³ forced simulations together with the coupled simulation (ARPEGE-Climat) EA7 used for S8.

5. Continental surface component

Representation of vegetation in seasonal forecasts is being addressed in the framework of the European project [H2020 CONFESS](#) (CONSistent representation of temporal variations of boundary Forcings in reanalysES and Seasonal forecasts). A possible evolution might be to consider an interactive Leaf Area Index instead of a climatology used in the current system, depending on the results from CONFESS. The reader is invited to refer to this project deliverables for more details.

6. Initial conditions, ensemble size and generation

6.1. Initial conditions: sea-ice

The first tests performed with NEMOv4.2+SI³ (see section 4.1.) show that there is hope to use sea ice initialization from a nudged coupled run with this new model instead of using those coming from a nudged forced NEMOv3.6+Gelato integration in our current S8.

6.2. Ensemble size:

The re-forecast ensemble size will be chosen, from a minimum of 25 members to a maximum of 51 members, according to the results of C3S2_370-WP4, and by finding a balance between computing costs related to model improvements and an optimal ensemble size.

6.3. Ensemble generation: 3 starting dates with same ensemble subsize

The current System 8 initialization is a three-tier lagged initialization: for a 51-member real-time forecast with initialization labelled as first of the month, one member actually uses the initial conditions from the first while two groups of 25 members are initialized on the prior and second prior Thursdays. However, there is actually a tendency to obtain better scores for ensembles having all their members starting the first of the month, in burst mode, as compared to ensembles with lagged initialization.

As an example, Table 6.3.1 shows seasonal hemispheric space correlations for the winter season (DJF) for the operational System 8 and the same forecasting system in burst mode S8b (see Section 3.2).

	S8	S8b
SH Z500	0.12 0.19 0.26	0.25 0.29 0.33
SH ST	0.26 0.29 0.32	0.33 0.35 0.37

Table 6.3.1. DJF space correlations with confidence intervals obtained by bootstrapping 10 members out of 25 for S8 and 10 members out of 15 for S8b.

From results shown in Table 6.3.1, we conclude that S8b is significantly better than S8. Therefore, it might be worthwhile readjusting the ratio of members across the dates of the lagged initialization by giving more weight to the first of the month. However, we still recommend to keep lagged dates

to account for uncertainty in the initial conditions and to comply with operational constraints. A possible solution would be to launch the same number of members on the three lagged dates, e.g. 17 members each to make a 51-member ensemble. This might be tested in the final phase of System 9 development if possible given higher priority development constraints.

6.4. Ensemble generation: possible removal of the Stochastic Dynamics (SD) at longer range

The initial goal of the Stochastic Dynamics approach (SD, Batté and Déqué 2016) was to enlarge the ensemble spread, tending to make the ratio spread over root mean square error closer to one, and possibly the correlation. The SD approach was particularly useful to correct large biases in atmospheric variables such as Z500, and a convenient way to generate ensemble spread, but had limited impact on seasonal forecast scores. Attempts to further refine the methodology imply running previously nudged integrations and the corresponding re-forecasts which is time and HPC-time consuming. With the implemented improvements to ARPEGE-Climat, it appears that using SD with the same settings as System 8 tends to degrade the Nino3.4 correlation for months 2-4 and at month 6. At same time, there are no significant improvements in seasonal hemispheric space correlations with SD.

As an example, SST time correlations averaged on the Nino3.4 box (over 1993-2015) are shown in Table 6.4.1, for the May initialization. Two experiments are considered, both based on the S9P6 atmospheric physics (see Section 3.1) and initialized with the same coupled nudged run. The first experiment called S9P6ci uses initial perturbations and while the second one called S9P6cids uses Stochastic Dynamics

	S9P6ci	S9P6cids
Months 2-4	<i>0.859</i>	<i>0.848</i>
Month 6	<i>0.831</i>	<i>0.807</i>

Table 6.4.1. Nino3.4 SST monthly time correlation from May start month of 1993-2015.

For months 2-4 and month 6, this table shows that S9P6ci correlation is significantly better than that of S9P6cids, at the significance level of 0.01 (estimated by bootstrapping ensemble members).

A possible solution would be to suppress SD after one or two months, in order to keep the benefit brought by the methodology in terms of ensemble spread and biases at shorter range, while avoiding the score decrease evidenced at longer range. Similar to changes in lagged initialization, it might be tested at the end of System 9 development, when modelling choices are settled, if it fits within the development timeline and constraints.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has reviewed the investigations carried out so far for the development of the new Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 9. The choices to be made are related to changes in the core components of the coupled model (atmosphere, ocean), representation of additional physical components of the climate system (aerosols, vegetation), initialization of sea ice and ensemble generation.

The choice of the new atmospheric component remains to be made between two new sets of physical parameterizations for ARPEGE-Climat that both improve seasonal forecast quality compared to the current System 8. This choice yet to be discussed will be guided by considerations of stability, forecast performance and possible maintenance in the CNRM climate modelling group. Regarding ocean, our present best choice will be to use the new version of NEMO (version 4.2) along with sea ice from SI³, although it remains conditioned to its performance in coupled mode. This ocean and sea ice modelling choice will also condition the initialization of sea ice, with hope that the initial states provided by a prior coupled nudged run will be satisfactory (i.e with enough sea ice). However, the inclusion of interactive aerosols and interactive leaf area index is more uncertain given the limited impact on scores and the increased complexity (e.g initialization of these new components). Finally, as far the forecasting setup is concerned, current results point to changing the balance of members across the lagged initialization, and removing the stochastic dynamics at an earlier stage of forecast integration.

8. References

Batté, L., and Déqué, M. (2016). Randomly correcting model errors in the ARPEGE-Climate v6.1 component of CNRM-CM: applications for seasonal forecasts. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 9: 2055-2016.

Bechtold, P., N. Semane, P. Lopez, J. Chaboureau, A. Beljaars, and N. Bormann, 2014: Representing Equilibrium and Nonequilibrium Convection in Large-Scale Models. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 71, 734–753.

Guérémy, J. F., 2011: A continuous buoyancy based convection scheme: one and three dimensional validation. *Tellus A*, 63, 687-706.

Hogan, R.J., and Bozzo, A., 2016: ECRAD: A new radiation scheme for IFS. *ECMWF Technical memorandum 787*.

Météo-France, 2021: Documentation for the Météo-France seasonal forecasting system 8. <http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/IMG/pdf/system8-technical.pdf>

Michou, M., Nabat, P., Saint-Martin, D., Bock, J., Decharme, B., Mallet, M., et al. (2020). Present-day and historical aerosol and ozone characteristics in CNRM CMIP6 simulations. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 12, e2019MS001816.

Pergaud, J., Masson, V., Malardel, S. et al. A Parameterization of Dry Thermals and Shallow Cumuli for Mesoscale Numerical Weather Prediction. Boundary-Layer Meteorol 132, 83–106 (2009).

Piriou, J. M., Redelsperger, J. L., Geleyn, J. F., Lafore, J. P., and Guichard, F. (2007). An approach for convective parameterization with memory: Separating microphysics and transport in grid-scale equations. Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences, 64, 4127-4139

Voltaire, A., Saint-Martin, D., Stnisi, S., Decharme, B., Alias, A., Chevallier, M., et al (2019). Evaluation of CMIP6 DECK experiments with CNRM-CM6-1. Journal of Advances in Modelinn Earth Systems, 11.

